

Monotheistic Pre-Islamic South Arabia

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Entry tags: Arabian Religions, Religious Group

This entry treats the state religion of Pre-Islamic South Arabia from the second half of the fourth century CE until the region was absorbed by the Sassanians in the seventh century CE. During this time, the ruling Himyarites not only expanded South Arabia to its largest territorial extent ever, spanning from modern Yemen to lower Iraq and perhaps even to Palestine (Robin, 2012), but they also adopted a new form of monotheism, which was heavily influenced by but distinct from Judaism. This Judaizing Himyarite Monotheism worshipped a monotheistic deity called either Raḥmānān “The Merciful” or ʾIlān “God.” While details about this religion are sparse, Philostorgius provides some hints concerning its character. He records that Constantius II sent an expedition to Himyarites (called “Homeritae”) in South Arabia in what would be the time of Thaʾrān Yuhanʾim (324-375 CE). He describes the Himyarites as “of the Israelitish family” but notes that they sacrificed to various native gods. There were also Jews in the royal court, who are said to unsuccessfully oppose the Christian embassy, as Philostorgius alleges that the Himyaritic king converted to Christianity and built three churches. Yet during that time, public state sponsorship of polytheism did not cease in the epigraphic record. It is not until the reign of Thaʾrān’s son, Malkīkarib Yuhaʾmin (375-400 CE; Robin, 2012), that worship in the monumental display texts was almost unilaterally directed to Raḥmānān, with mentions of the old gods becoming almost extinct (yet, they still persist in the less public stick inscriptions; Stein, 2009). Explicitly Jewish inscriptions also begin appearing in fourth century CE; albeit, the exact relationship of South Arabian Judaism with other outside contemporary Jewish groups remains unclear (Hughes, 2020a). There is further uncertainty as to whether their God, who is twice explicitly called “The Lord of the Jews,” was originally identified via syncretism with Raḥmānān or if he was thought to be a separate distinct but still monotheistic divinity, who existed alongside Raḥmānān (Gajda, 2017). Regardless of this potential distinction, the name Raḥmānān does eventually get absorbed into local Christian and Jewish vocabulary as a moniker for “God.” During the fifth century CE, the state continues to sponsor Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism all-the-while tensions between Christians and Jews begin to rise. The Martyrdom of Azqir (Conti-Rossini, 1910) records a priest named Azqir being arrested for proselytizing. He was then brought to trial before the Himyarite king (who is not said to be Jewish) and the Jews on his court. The text ends with Azqir’s martyrdom, with the narrator noting that thirty eight Christians had received a similar fate during that king’s reign. In the sixth century CE, state sponsorship of Judaizing Himyarite Monotheism disappears as the Ethiopian Aksumites gradually gained control of South Arabia and installed a Christian king, Maʾdīkarib Yaʾfur, on the South Arabian throne in 519 CE. Around this time, the Christians began to persecute the Jews. When Maʾdīkarib dies a few years later in 522 CE, a Jewish prince named Yūsuf Asʾar Yathʾar (Arabic Dhū Nuwās) began a series of military campaigns seeking to expel the Aksumites and to burn their churches (Robin, 2012). This culminated in the slaying of the Martyrs of Najrān in 523 CE, wherein the Jewish King Yūsuf gained control of Najrān by artifice and then systematically kills the Christians. This event gave justification for the Aksumite King Kaleb to invade South Arabia, during which he killed Yūsuf and violently seeks vengeance on the Jews. South Arabia thereafter would remain under Christian control until it was eventually acquired by the Sassanians.

Date Range: 360 CE - 570 CE

Region: Monotheistic South Arabia

Region tags: Asia, Western Asia, Saudi Arabia, Yemen

This is the region of the South Arabian homeland in which inscriptions from the Monotheistic Period are attested. However, I notably omit here the wādī

Ma'sal inscriptions, which are roughly 570 km northeast of this region and claim that the Himyarites submitted tribes who extended as far as lower Iraq. Robin (2012) posits that the Himyarites exercised control through almost all inner Arabia, with the possible exception of the historical oases towns in the southern Hijāz, which is the strip of land in modern Saudi Arabia that runs along the western coast of the Red Sea. Regardless of this broader claim of Himyarite control, political submission is not necessarily religious submission and the textual record leaves it unclear as to how thoroughly Himyarite monotheism would have been imposed in these regions outside the South Arabian homeland.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

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– Source 1 Description: Iwona Gajda's *Monothéisme en Arabie du Sud préislamique* (in French).

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– Source 1 Description: Yosef Yuval Tobi's survey of Himyaritic History, including the Monotheistic Period. While Himyarite monotheism was indeed Judaizing, one should be cautious of Tobi's overstatement that "Judaism became the official state religion" of the Himyarites. This fails to explain the lack of explicit Jewish language in state-sponsored monotheistic inscriptions of the fourth to fifth centuries CE. For a more balanced approach, see Gajda's online article above or Hughes 2020a: 32-34.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Himyarites expanded South Arabia to its largest territorial extent in history, which would have resulted in contact with outside religious groups. However, sadly there is not much data on this

interaction. Within the South Arabian homeland, polytheism continued without official state-sponsorship. When Himyaritic Judaizing Monotheism was the state religion in the fourth and fifth centuries CE, Jews are recorded on the royal court. Philostorgius's record of the construction of three churches implies that Christians were present as well since at least the fourth century CE, albeit in the fifth century CE a Himyaritic king accused Azqir of spreading a "new religion" (However, the same king is also said to have thirty eight Christian evangelists killed). Various violent conflicts break out between Jews and Christians in the early sixth century CE, during which pagans are also attested in Najrān and seem uninvolved in the violent events that unfold.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Jews and the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheists are accommodating of each other. No violent conflict is recorded between them and the polytheists in the South Arabian homeland during this period, either.

– No

Notes: The Jews and the Christians are frequently in conflict (whether violent or not) with one another. The Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism also appears to penalize Christian evangelism.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: In the sixth century CE, the Book of the Himyarites and letters of Simeon of Beth Arsham record that Yūsuf's state-sponsored Judaism actively sought to convert Christians to Judaism under the penalty of death. In fact, the inscription Ry 508 classifies Yūsuf's military victories as the promulgation of Raḥmānān's mercy. There, one of Yūsuf's men commemorates the king's victories against the Ethiopians and petitions Raḥmānān for further martial success. The text then ends with "Set your mercy over all the world, oh Raḥmānān. You are Lord!" This inscription appears to further paint Yūsuf's

wars as a means of religious proselytization. The spread of state monotheism through war was not Yūsuf's innovation, however. The fifth century text Ry 520 implies that Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism had earlier sought Raḥmānān's promulgation through battle. There, the dedicant petitions his God for "healthy sons, going on (military) expeditions for the name of Raḥmānān."

Reference: Ry 520

Reference: Ry 508

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytization coercive:
– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:
– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:
– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Syriac Book of the Himyarites and the letters of Simeon Beth-Arsham state that when Yusuf conquered Najrān, he martyred the Christians unless they proclaimed that Jesus was only a man (and not God) and converted to Judaism. After Yusuf was killed and the Ethiopians took over, King Kaleb offered amnesty for those Christians who had apostatized and ordered the priests to hold special service for their forgiveness. However, the former apostates were then prohibited from taking

sacraments for a year.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: After Yūsuf was defeated, there were former Christians in Najrān who had renounced Christ and converted to Judaism under the threat of death. These individuals approach Kaleb when he takes over and give a penitent speech: “[W]e have committed wrong and done wickedness and provoked (God's) anger... for we willingly have killed our souls...[O]ur mouth is shut before God and before man and there is no excuse for us in anything at all, [except] in that we are ashamed before heaven [and] before the dwellers of the earth and also before (Kaleb's) palace.” Kaleb then provides a reassuring speech, gives them amnesty, and tells the priests to hold a special service for their forgiveness. The only penalty that the apostates face is that they are barred from the sacraments for a year (Moberg, 1924: cxxxix-cxlii).

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– No

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: While there is little evidence for a translation of either the Old or New Testament into Sabaic, state-sponsored Himyarite Judaizing monotheism in the fourth to fifth centuries CE was most likely aware of the Bible and revered it to some degree, especially given the arguments between Christians and Jews on the royal court recorded by Philostorgius and the Martyrdom of Azqir. Furthermore, an image of a Torah case is attested on a personal seal and possibly on one of Yūsuf's inscriptions (Robin, 2015: 273). The Najrānites also reference scripture in the Book of the Himyarites and the letters of Simeon of Beth Arsham. The South Arabian king Yūsuf is said to falsely swear by the “Torah” (Moberg, 1924: cv; Shahîd, 1971: 45, 50) while his friend is said to swear by the “Gospels” (Shahîd, 1971: 56). Additionally, a reference appears to be made to 1 John 2:4 (“he is a liar and the truth is not in him”) when one of the martyrs tells Yūsuf: “[Y]ou were a liar and... truth (does not) reside in you” (Shahîd, 1971: 51). A martyr who is unveiled also states “with unveiled face I am going to Christ,” which appears to reference 2 Corinthians 3:8 “All of us with unveiled faces see the glory of the Lord...” (Shahîd, 1971: 58).

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Field doesn't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Both synagogues and churches are known to have been constructed (and destroyed) in South Arabia during this period.

- ↳ Tombs:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Cemeteries:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Temples:
 - Yes

- ↳ Altars:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional markers:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Images of menorahs have been found at a synagogue, on rock surfaces, and on personal seals. An engraving of a Torah scroll case was found on a personal seal and possibly on one of Yūsuf's inscriptions (Robin, 2015: 271-273). For Christians, the Book of the Himyarites records temporary cross tattoos (Moberg, 1924: cxxxviii) in addition to bronze crosses, which could be sewed into garments (Moberg, 1924: cxxii, cxxv).

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
– On persons
– Some public spaces
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans:
 - No
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The Christian rulers in the 6th century CE would have believed in a soul, as evidenced by the beliefs of Christian martyrs in the Book of Himyarites.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In South Arabian Judaism and the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism, there is no definitive evidence for a spirit-body distinction. While the word for “soul(s)” (nfs¹/fs¹) is attested during this time in Sabaic texts, this noun could function reflexively and refer merely to “oneself.” If this were the case, there would be no spiritual implications (Robin, 2015: 148-151).

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sabaic inscriptions from this period never refer to an afterlife or resurrection, but they do mention "just death" (mwt šdqm). The only text from Yemen that definitely refers to an afterlife is an unprovenanced bilingual Aramaic/Sabaic epitaph, wherein the Aramaic section refers to "eternal life" but the Sabaic counterpart does not. This might have implied a difference of beliefs between the two cultures (Robin, 2015: 148-151).

– Yes

Notes: The Christian rulers in the sixth century CE would have believed in an afterlife.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god Raḥmānān was thought to reside "in the heavens" (CIH 543/1; Ja 857/3) and be the "Lord of the Heavens and the Earth," which denotes his possession of them (Ry 508/10). Raḥmānān was also believed to have created everything (Gar Bayt al-Ashwal 1/3) and is called the "Lord of Life and Death" (Gar Bayt al-Ashwal 1/2).

Reference: Ry 508

Reference: Ja 857

Reference: CIH 543

Reference: Gar Bayt al-Ashwal 1

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In war, one imagines that Raḥmānān would be acting towards the enemies negatively.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Immediately prior to this period, Philostorgius does record that the Himyarites sacrificed to other gods and polytheism certainly continues while the state sponsored monotheism dominates. It is also possible that some inscriptions perceived of and invoked two separate monotheistic deities- "Raḥmān" and the "Lord of the Jews." However, these deities may also have been perceived of as the same entity.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Oracles were present in South Arabia before the monotheistic period, albeit none from Raḥmān have yet been recovered.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: While references to non-divine supernatural entities used to be plentiful in the South Arabian epigraphic record, they fall out in the Monotheistic Period. There is a reference to evil spirits in one of the letters of Simeon Beth-Arsham. There, the Jews proclaim a maidservant to be the “Satan of the Christians,” stating “there is no evil spirit that does not reside in her.” Prior to this, the narrator described her as having “led a wicked life” that was “loud-tongued... insolent... hated by everyone... masculine in all her deeds... even her masters used to fear her because of her wickedness.” She also claims to have stripped herself naked in front of men and women multiple times (Shahîd, 1971: 55-56). The belief here seems to be that spirits could possess people and cause them to commit socially unsanctioned and disruptive deeds. The causality of this appears to be indirect rather than direct, as the spirits do not seem to be assigned direct responsibility for her actions, but rather seem to make her inclined to act in certain manners.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Confer the note on “Non-human supernatural beings are present” above. There appears to be a conception of God and also evil spirits, including Satan, at least by the sixth century CE. Additionally, South Arabian Christianity had the conception of the Trinity, as shown in CIH 541/1-3: “By the power, aid, and mercy of Raḥmānān, his Messiah, and the Holy Spirit.”

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: There is no kinship organization in Judaism and the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism.

– Yes

Notes: South Arabian Christianity in the sixth century CE holds to an explicit kinship model, with Jesus Christ as the son of Raḥmānān. This is explicated in RES 3904/16 “In the name of Raḥmānān and his son Christ.”

Reference: RES 3904

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: For Jewish, Himyarite Judaizing Monotheistic, and Christian beliefs, Raḥmānān is the high God and is therefore at top, even if there is no one else below him. Additionally, when the Jews refer to evil spirits in one of the letters of Simeon of Beth Arsham, they mention “Satan,” who is implied to be at the top of the evil spirit hierarchy (Shahīd, 1971: 55-56)

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: Raḥmānān's power is universal.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Notes: For lesser spiritual entities, the possible regional limitations on their power is unknown.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Notes: For Judaism and Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism.

– Yes [specify]: In Christianity, there is the Trinity.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Raḥmānān is petitioned to hear prayers (ATM 425/2; RES 4109/1; YM 1950/2), which implies monitoring.

Reference: ATM 425

Reference: RES 4109

Reference: YM 1950

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Confer “Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths” below.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Yūsuf is recorded by the Syriac authors as making a false oath (Moberg, 1924: cv; Shahîd, 1971: 44-45, 50) and is even chided by one the martyrs for this (Shahîd, 1971: 50). Another martyr reprimands Yūsuf's friend for falsely swearing that Yūsuf was a Christian previously (Shahîd, 1971: 56). In Yūsuf's own letter, he justifies his behavior by stating "it seemed to me that it was not worthwhile to be truthful towards Christians" (Guidi, 1881: 482-483). Overall, the various sources seem to agree that God cares about oaths, with Yūsuf justifying the violation of his oath by arguing that the Christians were unworthy of the truth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Apostatized Himyarite Christians are barred from taking sacraments for a year, implying that God cares about the performance of rituals (Moberg, 1924: cxli-cxlii).

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is probable that Jews and the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheists believed that God cared about ritual, no evidence for this has yet surfaced.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Confer “Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members” above.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: For Judaism and the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism, punishment is never explicitly stated but it is implied in the fragmentary text CIH 539, wherein the petitioners seek forgiveness from Raḥmānān for some sin, which probably entails possible punishment. For Christianity, the Book of the Himyarites makes clear that Yūsuf and his companions were killed when “the Lord wrought a great and extremely severe slaughter by the hand of the [Ethiopians]” for the martyrdom of the Najrānites (Moberg, 1924: cxxxv).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Military conquest by people can be seen as the wrath of God, as the Book of Himyarites makes clear.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In the two textually attested incidents, the reason appears to be known.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Vengeance.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that there were times when supernatural punishment was perceived as occurring but its cause was not known. Prior to the Monotheistic Period, individuals sometimes sought oracles when they were not certain as to which divinity they angered and/or what the occasion of the anger was. A similar uncertainty as to the Raḥmānān's perceived anger might have continued into the Monotheistic Period; albeit, records of this have yet to surface.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Confer "Belief in afterlife." The Jews and Judaizing Himyarite Monotheists never emphasize the afterlife and it is unclear if they even believed in it.

– Yes

Notes: The Himyarites who apostatize during the Martyrdom of Najrān repent to the Christian Ethiopian King Kaleb and state proclaim "we willingly have killed our souls." This implies that

punishment might be meted out after these individuals die.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Raḥmānān is able to grant good fortune and health to his supplicants (RES 5011 A + B/2). Additionally, one individual asks him to provide his family with “just lives” and “just deaths” (Ry 520/6-7) while another petitioner seeks an appropriate “beginning and end” (Gar nuove iscrizioni 4/8). Raḥmānān is also capable of providing individual with a life satisfying to the God (Sadd Ma’rib 6/13-14). King Abraha once credits Raḥmānān with stopping a plague (but not for starting it in the first place; CIH 541/92-93). Various kings also thank Raḥmānān for military victory (Ja 1028; Ry 506; Ry 507).

Reference: Ry 507

Reference: Ry 506

Reference: Ja 1028

Reference: CIH 541

Reference: Sadd Ma’rib 6

Reference: Gar nuove iscrizioni 4

Reference: Ry 520

Reference: RES 5011 A + B

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear if the Jews or the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheists believed in an afterlife.

– Yes

Notes: Christian South Arabia in the sixth century AD would have believed in rewards in the afterlife, which can be inferred by the Martyrs of Najrān. One letter of Simeon of Beth Arsham records martyrs receiving their “crown” (Shahīd, 1971: 48, 49, 54, 55), with a certain martyr saying “with unveiled face I am going to Christ... From now onward, peace and tranquility will <reign> among the people of Christ” (58). In the Book of the Himyarites, a wealthy martyr says

that Christ “will also in the new world deem me worthy of unspeakable wealth” (Moberg, 1924: cxxx).

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:
– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there are no direct references in the South Arabian textual references, it seems probable that the Jews followed their dietary laws. If this were the case, it is also possible that the Himyarite Judaizing Monotheism of the fourth to fifth centuries CE followed some dietary restrictions as well.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Philostorgius records that the Himyarites practiced "circumcision on the eighth day," which they probably adopted from the local Jews who are recorded among the aristocracy during that time.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is likely the state-sponsored monotheisms of this period required accepting certain ethical precepts, there is no evidence yet that membership in South Arabia required such adherence. This is contrary to Hughes (2020a: 34), who proposes that the Himyarite monotheism introduced ethical reforms. However, the supposed example of an ethical law that he provides comes from the polytheistic period.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: While individual monotheists in South Arabia were marginalized by out-groups, the ruling state monotheism would not require marginalization as it would be in power.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Christian practice of the sacraments are recorded in the Book of Himyarites. Communion could have been a large-scale ritual.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Proper doctrine does seem to be important as those who apostatize in the Book of the Himyarites (which contextually is by denying the teachings of the faith) are barred from the sacraments.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: In the Book of the Himyarites, the priests were over the sacraments, which would imply supervision of their practice.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: For communion, wine would be necessary.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: For non-Christian monotheists, a requirement to participate in local large-scale rituals are unknown. However, kings do record the construction of mikrabs, which were either shrines or

synagogues. The existence of these would imply the practice of large-scale rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: Tattoos of crosses are temporarily used to mark Christians during the second Ethiopian invasion (Moberg, 1924: cxxxviii).

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, for most of this period, evidence for tattoos/scarification to mark those in-group is lacking.

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Confer “Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?”

↳ Hair:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dress:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Ornaments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Older religious words such as “Amen” and “Adonai” can be used.

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: I choose "empire" here because the Himyarites managed to conquer most of central Arabia during this time period.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: There were various tribes within the state, which probably could have their own local bureaucratic apparati.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Two texts, CIH 540 and CIH 541, commemorate the costly repairs of the Marib Dam undertaken by two kings.

Reference: CIH 540

Reference: CIH 541

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Notably, in RES 5085 some individuals claim to undertake irrigation work with the help of their tribes and various other individuals.

Reference: RES 5085

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Evidence for taxation is sadly indirect. Two texts, CIH 540 and CIH 541, record in detail the efforts of two different kings to repair the Marib dam. In both these texts, there are lists of large sums of comestibles that the kings paid to the workers, which would require a system of taxation to accumulate.

Reference: CIH 540

Reference: CIH 541

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the Book of the Himyarites, Yūsuf refers to "the sentence of judges who rightly administer justice between us" (Moberg, 1924: cvii), which would then result in Yūsuf fining the Najrānites. This

implies that there could be autonomous judges that functioned outside of the royal veil.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: In the fifth century CE, both the king and local autonomous groups appear to have been able to enforce institutionalized punishment. In the Sabaic stick inscription X.BSB 152/8-9, an official from the tribe ḡ-Gdnm threatens some individuals who were planning to attack others that “the custody of the king and of ḡ-Gdnm” will be upon them if they proceed, implying that the tribe of ḡ-Gdnm had penal authority in addition to the king. The fifth century CE is also the setting of the Martyrdom of Azqir, wherein the priest Azqir is seized and imprisoned by the authority of local elders for spreading Christianity. He is then sent to appear at the capital Ṣafar before the king and his court, wherein the king sentences Azqir to return to Najrān and be executed by the elders. During that same king’s reign, thirty eight other Christians are said to be martyred in this manner as well. As for the sixth century CE, the Book of the Himyarites and letters of Simeon of Beth Arsham record that Yūsuf fines the Najrānites silver and gold, promising not to take their property (implying that he could). Additionally, he severs the limbs of Christians and sentences them to death if they do not convert to Judaism.

Reference: Peter Stein. Die altsüdarabischen Minuskelschriften auf Holzstäbchen aus der Bayerischen Staatsbibliothek in München. Tübingen: Wasmuth.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group’s adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Confer the notes on the previous two questions. Given that there were institutions aside from royalty that could also execute individuals and decide in cases involving the king himself, individuals appear to have been subject to these institutions’ punishments as well.

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
 - Yes

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
 - Yes

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
 - Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

- ↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:
 - Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The South Arabian state uses Sabaic as its written language during this period but the use of Sabaic is not limited only to the state and its religion. Furthermore, whether formal scribal training in Sabaic was limited to the state remains unknown.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Confer the section on "Taxation" above. In the sixth century CE, there are records of kings paying workers with large sums of food. Albeit, the sum of comestibles is so large that it appears to be the result of taxation. While it is possible that the state had its own methods of food production, this

remains unknown.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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Reference: Sadd Ma'rib 6

Reference: CIH 541

Reference: Ja 1028

Reference: Ry 506

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Reference: Ry 508

Reference: Ry 520

Reference: YM 1950

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